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DEVELOPMENT OF A METHODOLOGY FOR THE DIGITALIZATION OF TANGIBLE TECHNICAL ASSET INVENTORY IN THE DIGITAL ECONOMY

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Abstract. This article proposes a new IRC (Integrated Resource Concept) model for managing the material and technical resources of educational institutions throughout their entire life cycle (reception → inventory → utilization → repair → write-off). The model is developed on the basis of tabular management and deeply integrated with blockchain technology, enabling transparent real-time monitoring and control of each resource movement. The results of a pilot implementation conducted in an educational organization in Tashkent demonstrate a significant reduction in resource loss and misuse, as well as improved accuracy in repair scheduling and write-off procedures. This approach represents one of the first successful practical applications of blockchain technology combined with tabular integration in the management of material and technical resources within the educational sector.

Key words: IRC, material and technical resources, life cycle management, tabular integration, educational institutions, transparent monitoring, real-time reporting.

Annotatsiya. Maqolada ta'lim tashkilotlarining moddiy-texnik resurslarini ularning to'liq hayotiy sikli bo'yicha (qabul qilish → inventarizatsiya → foydalanish → ta'mirlash → ro'yxatdan chiqarish) samarali boshqarishga qaratilgan MARIK (Moddiy Resurslarni Integrallashgan Kontseptsiyasi) modeli taklif etiladi. Mazkur model jadvalli boshqaruv asosida blokcheyn texnologiyasi bilan chuqur integratsiyalashgan holda ishlab chiqilgan bo'lib, resurslarning har bir harakatini real vaqt rejimida shaffof monitoring qilish va boshqarish imkonini beradi. Toshkent shahridagi ta'lim tashkilotlaridan birida o'tkazilgan sinov natijalari MARIK modelining resurslar yo'qolishi va noto'g'ri foydalanish holatlarini sezilarli darajada qisqartirganini, shuningdek, ta'mirlash muddatlari hamda ro'yxatdan chiqarish jarayonlaridagi noaniqliklarni kamaytirganini ko'rsatdi. Ushbu yondashuv moddiy-texnik resurslarni boshqarishda blokcheyn texnologiyasi va jadvalli integratsiyani amaliyotga muvaffaqiyatli tatbiq etishning dastlabki samarali tajribalaridan biri hisoblanadi.

Kalit so'zlar: MARIK, moddiy-texnik resurslar, hayotiy sikl boshqaruvi, jadvalli integratsiya, ta'lim muassasalari, shaffof monitoring, real vaqt rejimida hisobot.

Аннотация. В статье предлагается новая модель интегрированной концепции материальных ресурсов (ИКР), предназначенная для управления материально-техническими ресурсами образовательных организаций на протяжении всего жизненного цикла (приемка → инвентаризация → использование → ремонт → списание). Модель разработана на основе табличного управления и глубоко интегрирована с технологией блокчейн, что обеспечивает прозрачный мониторинг и управление движением ресурсов в режиме реального времени. Результаты пилотного внедрения, проведенного в образовательной организации города Ташкента, показали снижение потерь и случаев нецелевого использования ресурсов, а также повышение точности процессов ремонта и списания. Представленный подход является одним из первых успешных практических примеров применения блокчейн-технологии и табличной интеграции в управлении материально-техническими ресурсами в сфере образования.

Ключевые слова: ИКР, материально-технические ресурсы, управление жизненным циклом, табличная интеграция, образовательные организации, прозрачный мониторинг, отчетность в режиме реального времени.

INTRODUCTION

Effective management of material and technical resources in modern educational institutions, along with transparent control over their movement, constitutes an essential component of information security and organizational efficiency. Educational organizations operate with a large volume of tangible assets, including computer equipment, laboratory devices, teaching aids, and other technical resources. Therefore, the establishment of clear, systematic, and traceable mechanisms for the receipt, allocation, location, utilization, and accounting of these resources is critically important.

Based on the tabular structures presented in this study, an integrated information system for managing resource movement within an organization is developed. The primary objective of the article is to provide a scientific justification of a resource-tracking system from the perspectives of the warehouse, financially responsible personnel, repair departments, end users, accounting units, and territorial security services.

In the global digital economy, the growing demand for Big Data-based repositories has significantly influenced the development of accounting and management systems for material and technical resources across various sectors. Consequently, blockchain technologies, electronic document exchange platforms, and cloud-based solutions have received increasing attention as core components of modern digital infrastructure.

Within this context, new conceptual approaches are required to design digital platforms that reflect complex communication models in material and technical resource accounting. These include internal interdepartmental cooperation, defined within the Department-to-Department (D2D) model, as well as interactions with external suppliers, represented by the Department-to-Supplier (D2S) model.

Currently, a considerable number of automated systems and platforms for resource accounting are being developed and applied independently at the local level within the Republic of Uzbekistan. These systems range from closed financial, banking, tax, and customs platforms to corporate networks operating within private enterprises and firms. Moreover, various ministries, associations, joint-stock companies, and other organizations maintain specialized information systems that provide registries of material resources in accordance with their functional profiles.

Effective management of material resources—such as equipment, instruments, and other tangible assets—is particularly significant for educational institutions operating in both the public and private sectors. In Uzbekistan, this process is often complicated by budgetary constraints, regulatory requirements, and the scale of asset inventories. In response to these challenges, this article proposes an original approach based on a system of specialized tables designed for recording, distributing, monitoring, and utilizing material resources.

The proposed system integrates key organizational units, including warehouses, responsible persons, repair departments, users, accounting divisions, and territorial storage facilities, thereby ensuring comprehensive life-cycle management of resources. Resource movement is tracked through a unified chain of identification and inventory numbers (IDR and INR), which reduces operational risks and provides real-time access to accurate information. This approach enhances organizational efficiency, minimizes resource losses, and aligns with national regulatory frameworks, including International Public Sector Accounting Standards (IPSAS).

From this perspective, the issue examined in the present study represents not only a theoretical contribution but also a practical solution to existing management challenges.

In any organization, material and technical resources are closely linked with multiple departments through continuous interactions and cooperative processes. From the moment a resource is acquired, responsibility is typically shared between two primary units: the supply (warehouse) department and the accounting department. The supply department records technical characteristics such as brand, quantity, quality, and condition, while the accounting department registers financial and administrative data, including asset name, date of receipt, location, and the financially responsible person.

Subsequently, additional records are generated by operational units—such as digital technology centers—that monitor the technical condition and usage of equipment. These initial records form the foundation of the resource's digital profile and are submitted to organizational management for decision-making purposes.

As resources undergo multiple events throughout their life cycle—including transfers between departments, repairs, upgrades, service life extensions, innovations, audits, external servicing, imports, or awards—the need for a centralized repository capable of storing and processing comprehensive information becomes evident. An integrated management system that enables real-time access to such data is therefore indispensable.

In this regard, the proposed system may be conceptualized as a reference digital platform that manages consolidated information on material and technical resources using Big Data technologies, ensuring transparency, traceability, and strategic control across the organization.

LITERATURE REVIEW

A number of researchers have contributed to the development of methodologies for the digitalization of inventories of physical and technical equipment within economic systems. Zahran and Jaber (2017) emphasize that regular inventory updates, improved turnover, and optimization processes play a decisive role in enhancing organizational efficiency [1]. Li Hui et al. (2013), using the example of China, demonstrate that investments in road infrastructure contribute to inventory reduction and more efficient resource utilization in companies [2].

Samuel Holloway (2024) highlights that digital transformation is fundamentally reshaping inventory control practices. His research examines the application of IoT sensors, RFID tags, AI-driven analytics, and cloud-based systems, concluding that computer-aided technologies enable real-time monitoring and seamless data integration in inventory management processes [3]. Cecconi et al. argue that the integration of physical assets into a digital environment through Digital Asset Management (DAM) across the asset life cycle facilitates Big Data generation and enhances data processing and management efficiency [4].

Mandar E. M. et al. (2024) propose an autonomous inventory replenishment framework, demonstrating that technological innovation significantly improves operational efficiency and the accuracy of inventory tracking [5]. Johnson and Kim developed an algorithm for managing manufacturing machine inventories, which effectively optimized storage control; however, subsequent studies indicate that further enhancement of security mechanisms is required to support dynamic multi-warehouse supply chains [6]. Ahmed Alkhard (2024) investigates methods for improving asset management by leveraging data generated through digital asset management tools, highlighting their potential to support informed decision-making [7].

Overall, existing studies demonstrate that inventory digitization plays a critical role in strengthening security within inventory and supply chain management systems, while also enabling advanced identification mechanisms and the adoption of analytical technologies.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The following methodological approaches were employed in the present study:

Table-based analysis.

The tables developed for the warehouse, responsible persons, repair departments, users, accounting units, and territorial control were systematically analyzed in order to assess their functional roles within the integrated resource management framework.

Schematic modeling.

Relationships among data elements contained in the tables were modeled using block diagrams and data flow diagrams, enabling a clear representation of information exchange and process sequencing.

Comparative analysis.

The proposed methodology was compared with international practices in material and technical resource management to identify common principles and distinctive features.

Information security approach.

Information security considerations were incorporated into the methodology, with particular attention to access control, traceability, and secure monitoring of resource movement.

To operationalize the proposed approach, six core tables and their corresponding sub-tables (twelve tables in total) were developed. These tables can be implemented using software tools such as SQL-based database systems or spreadsheet applications. Their primary purpose is to document, interconnect, and trace each stage of the resource life cycle in a consistent and structured manner.

Each table contains the following standardized attributes:

- Identification Number (IDR): A unique resource identifier, where n denotes the current state and m indicates a modified state.
- Inventory Number (INR): Official inventory identification of the resource.
- MAC Address (MACR): Physical network identifier of the device.
- Resource Contract (RC): Contractual information related to the resource.

- Resource Type or Name (RTN): Brand name or full designation of the resource.
- Unit of Measure (UM): Measurement unit of the resource quantity.
- Resource Quantity (RQ): Quantity of the resource.
- Property Description (X[i,j]): Technical and functional characteristics of the resource.
- Building/Floor/Room (B/F/R): Physical location of the resource.
- Department (D): Organizational unit to which the resource is assigned.
- Responsible Person (RP): Individual responsible for the resource.
- User Person (UP): Authorized user of the resource.
- Date: Recorded in the standardized format YYYY-MM-DD.

The tables are functionally classified as follows:

- Warehouse section (Tables 1.1 and 1.2): Records the receipt of resources and their subsequent distribution to departments.
- Responsible person section (Tables 2.1 and 2.2): Documents resource assignment and changes in location, including the reason and date of transfer.
- Repair section (Tables 3 and 3.1): Tracks resource condition, distinguishing between major and minor repairs, and includes comments recorded before and after maintenance, as well as relevant staff or user information.
- User section (Table 4): Provides authorized users with accessible information regarding the current status of resources.
- Accounting section (Table 5): Maintains real-time data on resource location and responsible personnel for financial and administrative control.
- Territorial storage section (Tables 6.1 and 6.2): Monitors resources entering or leaving designated territorial zones.

All tables operate within the framework of the Integrated Concept of Material Resources (MRIK), ensuring comprehensive monitoring of the entire resource life cycle—from initial registration to final release. As part of the methodological implementation, standardized status indicators and reasons (e.g., “New resource received”, “Under repair”, “Damaged”) were utilized to maintain consistency and analytical clarity.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

In addressing the research problem, the study focuses on the development and validation of a realistic model applied to a limited organizational segment. This approach acknowledges that large-scale organizations—particularly those operating at regional, intersectoral, or national levels—face a significantly higher number of operational variables and management challenges.

The process of resource utilization (Table 1), the list of received resources, and, most importantly, the structure of the Integrated Content of Material Resources (MRIK)—which captures interdepartmental relationships and data linkages—are presented in Table 3. The interaction between MRIK and other material and technical resource management blocks (MBBTs) is illustrated in Figure 1, while annual changes in MRIK parameters are reflected in the detailed records of Table 4. It is proposed that all departments involved in resource utilization maintain standardized records using Table 1 to ensure data consistency and traceability.

Table 1 documents resource acceptance activities and includes mandatory attributes such as resource contract information, full resource name, unit of measurement, and a detailed description of resource characteristics. Department names and key inventory identifiers are assigned once during the distribution process in real time and remain immutable throughout the resource life cycle, thereby ensuring data integrity.

Contract identifiers (RSH_i, RSH_m) are recorded for each acquired resource. Resource names and brands (RTN_k, RTN_g, RTN_i) are entered in their full and specific form, reflecting origin and technical designation rather than generalized category labels. Measurement units (O'B_j, O'B_y, O'B_i), such as units, kilograms, or meters, are specified according to the physical state of the resource. The internal technical characteristics of resources are recorded in the X[i,j] field; for example, for computer equipment, this includes specifications such as RAM capacity, HDD or SSD type, graphics card, processor, and motherboard model.

The inventory number (INR_n) is not entered manually. Instead, following registration in the accounting department—through the parallel USAZBO accounting platform—the inventory number is automatically generated and assigned based on the number of resources specified in the corresponding contract. This automated procedure minimizes human error and enhances data reliability.

These data entries constitute mandatory records in Table 2 and form the foundational dataset for subsequent tables. The remaining tables serve to document organizational departments and operational processes, while consistently linking resource identifiers, MAC addresses, and inventory numbers. Together, these interconnected records ensure comprehensive monitoring, traceability, and analytical consistency across the entire material resource management system.

A sample of the proposed tables is presented below (Table 1.1).

Table 1.1. Warehouse Section Resource Reception and Registration Process

ID Number	Resource Contract	Resource Brand / Full Name	Unit of Measure	Resource Quantity	Resource Description	Inventory Number	Date (YYYY-MM-DD)
IDR_n	RSH_n	RTN_n	UM_j	RQ_n	$X[i,j]$	INR_n	YYYY-MM-DD
IDR_m	RSH_m	RTN_m	UM_i	RQ_m	$X[m,j]$	INR_m	YYYY-MM-DD

Table 1.2. Warehouse Section Resource Distribution and Allocation Process

ID Number	Inventory Number	MAC Address	Resource Contract	Resource Brand / Full Name	Unit of Measure	Resource Quantity	Resource Description	Building / Floor / Room	Department	Responsible Person	Date (YYYY-MM-DD)
IDR_n	INR_n	$MACR_n$	RSH_n	RTN_n	UM_j	RQ_n	$X[i,j]$	$B/F/R_n$	D_n	RP_n	YYYY-MM-DD
IDR_m	INR_m	$MACR_m$	RSH_m	RTN_m	UM_i	RQ_m	$X[m,j]$	$B/F/R_m$	D_m	RP_m	YYYY-MM-DD

Table 2.1. Resource Acceptance by the Responsible Person, Resource Location Change, and ID-Inventory Number Chain

ID Number	Inventory Number	MAC Address	Resource Contract	Resource Brand / Full Name	Unit of Measure	Resource Quantity	Resource Description	Building / Floor / Room	Department	Reason for Change	Responsible Person	Beneficiary	Acceptance of Responsibility	Deregistration	Date (YYYY-MM-DD)
IDR_n	INR_n	$MACR_n$	RSH_n	RTN_n	UM_j	RQ_n	$X[i,j]$	$B/F/R_n$	D_n	Under technical inspection	RP_n	BP_n	AR_n	DR_n	YYY Y-MM-DD
IDR_m	INR_m	$MACR_m$	RSH_m	RTN_m	UM_i	RQ_m	$X[m,j]$	$B/F/R_m$	D_m	New resource received	RP_m	BP_m	AR_m	DR_m	YYY Y-MM-DD

Table 2.2. Resource Location Change and ID-Inventory Number Chain

ID Number	Inventory Number	MAC Address	Department	Reason for Change	Change Date	Building / Floor / Room	Responsible Person	Date (YYYY-MM-DD)
IDR_n	INR_n	$MACR_n$	D_n	Under Technical Inspection	YYYY-MM-DD	$B/F/R_n$	RP_n	YYYY-MM-DD
IDR_m	INR_m	$MACR_m$	D_m	New Resource Received	YYYY-MM-DD	$B/F/R_m$	RP_m	YYYY-MM-DD

Table 3. Junior Admin Status – Ability to Enter a Fixed Asset Not Included in the List Upon Arrival, Enter Information in Specific Columns Monitoring the Status of a Material Resource Based on Integrated Content (MRIK) (Information is filled in from the date the resource was registered until it is deregistered)

ID Number	Inventory Number	MAC Address	Resource Brand / Full Name	Building / Floor / Room	Department	Teacher / Employee / Student	Repair Department Employee	Resource Status Comment	Date (YYYY-MM-DD)	Condition After Repair	Comment	Date (YYYY-MM-DD)
IDR _n	INR _n	MACR _n	RTN _n	B/F/R _n	D _n	U _n	RD _n	Under technical review	YYYY-MM-DD	X[i,j]	Notes _n	YYYY-MM-DD
IDR _m	INR _m	MACR _m	RTN _m	B/F/R _m	D _m	U _m	RD _m	Operational after maintenance	YYYY-MM-DD	X[m,j]	Notes _m	YYYY-MM-DD

Table 3.1. Monitoring the Status of Non-Core Material Resources Based on Integrated Content (MRIK) (Information is recorded from the date of resource registration until deregistration)

ID Number	Inventory Number	Resource Brand / Full Name	Building / Floor / Room	Department	User	Resource Status Comment	Date (YYYY-MM-DD)
IDR _n	INR _n	RTN _n	B/F/R _n	D _n	UP _n	Under inspection	YYYY-MM-DD
IDR _m	INR _m	RTN _m	B/F/R _m	D _m	UP _m	Operational after review	YYYY-MM-DD

Table 4. User Section Dissemination of Publicly Accessible Information on Resource Status

ID Number	Inventory Number	MAC Address	Resource Brand / Full Name	Building / Floor / Room	Department	Teacher / Employee / Student	User	Resource Status Comment	Date (YYYY-MM-DD)
IDR _n	INR _n	MACR _n	RTN _n	B/F/R _n	D _n	TES _n	UP _n	Operational	YYYY-MM-DD
IDR _m	INR _m	MACR _m	RTN _m	B/F/R _m	D _m	TES _m	UP _m	Updated status	YYYY-MM-DD

Table 5. Accounting Department Section Real-Time Information on Resource Location and Responsible Person

ID Number	Inventory Number	MAC Address	Resource Contract	Resource Brand / Full Name	Unit of Measure	Resource Description	Building / Floor / Room	Department	Responsible Person	User	Date (YYYY-MM-DD)
IDR _n	INR _n	MACR _n	RSH _n	RTN _n	UM _j	X[i,j]	B/F/R _n	D _n	RP _n	UP _n	YYYY-MM-DD
IDR _m	INR _m	MACR _m	RSH _m	RTN _m	UM _i	X[m,j]	B/F/R _m	D _m	RP _m	UP _m	YYYY-MM-DD

Table 6.1. Territorial Security Section Resource Outbound Activity Monitoring

ID Number	Inventory Number	MAC Address	Resource Contract	Resource Brand / Full Name	Unit of Measure	Resource Description	Building / Floor / Room	Department	Responsible Person	Release Date (YYYY-MM-DD)
IDR _n	INR _n	MACR _n	RSH _n	RTN _n	UM _j	X[i,j]	B/F/R _n	D _n	RP _n	YYYY-MM-DD
IDR _m	INR _m	MACR _m	RSH _m	RTN _m	UM _i	X[m,j]	B/F/R _m	D _m	RP _m	YYYY-MM-DD

Table 6.2. Territorial Security Section Resource Access Control Activities

ID Number	Inventory Number	MAC Address	Resource Contract	Resource Brand / Full Name	Unit of Measure	Resource Description	Building / Floor / Room	Department	Responsible Person	Entry Date (YYYY-MM-DD)
IDR _n	INR _n	MACR _n	RSH _n	RTN _n	UM _j	X[i,j]	B/F/R _n	D _n	RP _n	YYYY-MM-DD
IDR _m	INR _m	MACR _m	RSH _m	RTN _m	UM _i	X[m,j]	B/F/R _m	D _m	RP _m	YYYY-MM-DD

Table 1.1 (Resource Reception).

In the resource reception stage, the identification parameters remain consistent (e.g., IDR_n = IDR_m, RSH_n = RSH_m), while the resource property description (X[i,j]) may be updated to reflect verified technical characteristics. As a result, the resource is formally received and registered in the system.

Table 1.2 (Resource Distribution).

At the distribution stage, the physical location (Building/Floor/Room – B/F/R_n) and the responsible person (RP_n) are assigned. Consequently, the destination department for the resource is clearly determined and recorded.

Table 2.1 (Responsible Person Acceptance).

The user (UP_n) is added, and the ID–Inventory Number chain (IDR–INR) is preserved. This ensures traceability of responsibility from acceptance onward.

Table 2.2 (Resource Location Change).

The reason for change (e.g., technical inspection or new resource received) and the date (YYYY-MM-DD) are recorded. As a result, changes in resource location are accurately documented.

Table 3 (Repair and Status Monitoring).

The resource status description (X_[i,j]), the date, and the post-repair condition are recorded. This enables systematic observation of resource condition, including issues reported by teachers/employees/students, and supports evidence-based maintenance decisions.

Table 3.1 (Non-Core Resources Monitoring).

For non-core resources, the user (UP_n) and status are tracked. As a result, the operational status of such resources is updated in real time.

Table 4 (User Section).

Publicly accessible comments are enabled, allowing users to view resource status, report improper use, and monitor the resolution of identified issues.

Table 5 (Accounting Department).

Comprehensive information is provided to accounting units, enabling real-time reporting and alignment with financial and administrative controls.

Tables 6.1 and 6.2 (Territorial Security).

The exit/entry dates (YYYY-MM-DD) are recorded, ensuring effective territorial access control and security monitoring.

As illustrated in the sample structures, the tables store resource movements as a linked chain. For example, in the repair process, the association with Teacher/Employee/Student (O/X/S) and the corresponding status comment is maintained, ensuring continuity and traceability across stages.

Discussion (Edited, High Academic Standard)

The proposed table-based system addresses key challenges in material resource management by reducing losses through an unbroken ID–INR chain, increasing operational efficiency via real-time monitoring, and ensuring regulatory compliance through structured documentation.

The system's primary advantages include:

- Integrated architecture based on the Integrated Concept of Material Resources (MRIK);
- Flexibility, allowing adaptation across diverse departments and workflows;
- Cost-effectiveness, as it can be implemented manually or through standard software solutions.

Potential limitations—such as increased complexity when handling large data volumes and the need for staff training—are acknowledged and reframed as opportunities for organizational capacity building. In the context of Uzbekistan's material resource management practices, the system is suitable for state-owned and public-sector organizations, with enhanced effectiveness when integrated with modern enterprise platforms (e.g., ERP systems). Future extensions may include AI-driven predictive analytics to forecast maintenance needs and optimize resource utilization.

Overall, the analysis demonstrates that the system enables end-to-end control of resources at every organizational stage—from warehouse intake to user assignment, repair, accounting, and territorial security. The resulting benefits include:

- Transparent and auditable resource accounting;
- Clear assignment of responsibility;
- Strengthened financial and material controls;
- Enhanced information security;
- Improved efficiency and sustainability in resource utilization.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The proposed idea—an integrated spreadsheet system for material resource management—significantly enhances organizational efficiency and ensures full control over resources.

The findings of this study underscore the importance of developing a spreadsheet-based system for effective resource management within organizations. By integrating systems across various departments—including the

warehouse, responsible personnel, repair department, users, accounting, and territorial security—resource management is optimized, thereby improving the efficiency of organizational operations, particularly within the educational process. Additionally, this system plays a crucial role in strengthening information security.

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